

**Proceedings of the
2019
Society of Wood Science and
Technology
International Convention**

**Convention Theme: Renewable
Materials and the Wood-based
Bioeconomy**

Edited by Susan LeVan-Green

*Overall General Chair: Eve Haviarova,
Purdue University, USA*

**October 20-25, 2019
Tenaya Lodge
Yosemite National Park, California, USA**

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**Data Science at the University of Primorska: Combining Fundamentals with
Data and Challenges from Buildings, Wood and Processing Science**

Dr. Mike Burnard
InnoRenew CoE & University of Primorska
Prof. Klavdija Kutnar
University of Primorska

Abstract

The University of Primorska has developed a new master's degree program within the Faculty of Mathematics, Natural Sciences, and Information Technology (FAMNIT). This innovative program teaches data science fundamentals using data and challenges from wood science, wood value chains (processing, logistics), and building science. Data science is an interdisciplinary field blending computer science, mathematics, and domain knowledge. Key computer science skills like data management, algorithm development, parallel and distributed computing, and visualization are taught alongside topics in mathematics including statistics, probability theory, algebra, and graph theory to provide students with the skills necessary to collect, store, process, and analyze data to provide value insights to scientific work and industry. The novelty of FAMNIT's data science program is the inclusion of specialized domain knowledge from the fields of wood science, processing, tracking, and logistics in wood value chains, and data collected from sensors in buildings.

As new devices are developed, wood scientists have found novel uses of them to provide new insights and wood assessment techniques. For example, as prices drop on tools like near infrared (NIR) spectrometers they can be deployed in wood production lines to provide useful quality management information (amongst other uses). The chemometric data produced by a single NIR device is significant, but as more and more devices are deployed there is a need to develop solutions that provide rapid and insightful information to users (production staff, managers, etc.). Scalable solutions require interdisciplinary skills data scientists can provide, but to generate truly useful information domain knowledge from wood science and processing is required. Another example is creating advanced tag and trace systems in chain-of-custody applications that may combine multiple technologies like radio frequency identification, blockchain, and integration with existing enterprise resource planning software and life cycle assessment impact databases.

Sensors deployed in buildings allow researchers and manufacturers to gain insight into product and system performance in buildings. For example, monitoring temperature, relative humidity, vibrations, strain, etc. in cross-laminated timber plates can help researchers and manufacturers to optimize product and process design, engineers to improve seismic, acoustic, and wind-load design, and facilities managers to predict maintenance intervals and improve building energy performance. Sensors in buildings are also used to monitor indoor environments and users, which introduces both ethical and privacy issues that data scientists from FAMNIT's new program are prepared to confront.

The data science master's at FAMNIT is a 2-year program requiring a thesis and industry internships to ensure students are prepared to advance in both as academics and professionals. The program leverages FAMNIT's excellent research and teaching staff from existing computer science, mathematics, and sustainable building programs along with expertise from its partners in industry and external research organizations.

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